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Business Plan - Web-Based Smartphone Repair Service

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to create a dynamic website that provides information about the price of spare parts are updated every day and can be easily accessed by various types of smartphones, and perform financial planning analysis using financial statements, among others: income statement, cash flow statement. Then use the financial report in the form of net present value (NPV), payback period (PP) and return on investment (ROI)

Business plan in this research is done by using strategic analysis method, namely Porter's 5 forces, business model canvas, marketing mix, and financial analysis. After the planning, it was found that the business of repairing Smartphone is feasible to do and very profitable because the Return on Investment (ROI) which obtained from the average financial analysis is 30.28% per year

Keywords: *business plan; web portal; Porter's 5 forces; business model canvas*

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid technological developments in the current era of globalization have provided many benefits in the progress not only in big cities, but also in small towns as well. The benefits of technological development is supported by several factors, namely, the use of computers, mobile phones, and internet are already common and evenly distributed.

The convenience provided by the internet is widely used by the community to assist them in promoting the goods and services they sell, the promotion is usually done through social media or websites. Therefore, many conveniences provided by the internet, causing many companies interested to participate in utilizing internet facilities as a means of promotion of products and services.

Broad Internet access for the community, many parties use it to expand the business network. For example, the mushrooming of the establishment of Marketplace or Online Store in Indonesia, which little by little can replace the existence of conventional stores, and even superior because of time and time is not limited.

In this research will be created a business plan to provide a website which can be media for the customer to book a service by online, All reservations are made online and customers do not need to come to the premises, but we as technician provider will come to our customers.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Smartphone penetration in Indonesia has now reached more than 40%. That is, there are about 65 million smartphones that circulate here until the year 2016. This year, smartphone population estimates can reach 75 million. And, according to Ericsson in Mobility Report for Southeast Asia and Oceania, predicted in 2021, the number of smartphones in circulation in this country could reach 250 million.

Viewed habits, the majority of Indonesia's population access the internet through a smartphone. Then, when referring to Indonesia Netizen Survey 2015 research from MarkPlus, netizen average internet access for 6 hours per day. Looking at the facts mentioned above, the potential of the smartphone experienced technical disturbance is very large.

Looking at the current number of smartphones and their potential in the future will definitely be a very good market for service providers, either independent or under direct vendors. This is what makes smartphone and other gadget repair services keep popping up. Buyers who want to use the repair service, in general, are still running conventionally where every customer has to go to the repair service center. Limitations are time spent, especially busy customers that require a more efficient way.

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Seeing this problem the author sees the opportunity to plan the business planning of a web-based smartphone repair service that can meet the needs of the community. The author wants to create a web-based portal platform that will provide potential buyers with a complete list of repair service fees.

The formulations of the issues to be raised in this study are:

1. How to design a web-based smartphone repair service that can meet the needs of potential customers related repair services and information regarding repair service costs?
2. Is the financial planning of the bussiness plan can return capital in accordance with the specified time period?

3. SEGMENTS OF A BUSINESS PLAN

The business plans usually, consists of the following segments (Bygrave and Andrew Zacharakis 2011)

- The cover
- Executive summary
- Table of contents
- Industry, Customer and Competitor Analysis
- Company and Product Description
- Marketing plan
- Operational plan
- Development plan
- Team
- Critical risks
- Offering
- Financial plan
- Appendices

3.1. The Cover

The cover of the business plan contains information: company name, contact person, company address, phone number, fax, email, a disclaimer.

3.2. Executive summary

The most important part of the business plan, it needs to be added information about the business concept, industry, target market, business model, competitive advantage, team, and supply.

3.3. Table of Contents

Is a table of contents, must be included to facilitate in reading and looking for content from business plan Should include title, subheads, supporting attachments and other sections.

3.4. Industry, Customer and Competitor Analysis

- Industry: Describe the overall market position and targeted growth, future income and trends related to the business plan.
- Customer: Once the market share is known, the next step is to determine the target customer. Determination of customer can by determining information demography, behavior and psychography.
- Competitor analysis: Comparing our company with competitors in a similar business.

3.5. Company and Product Description

Describe the company and the product to be produced. Also an explanation of the company's vision and mission.

3.6. Marketing plan

In this section are descriptions of the target market strategy

- Target Market Strategy
Targeting and positioning products should be based on information obtained from customer analysis.

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- **Product / Service Strategy**
Describe what services will be provided to customers and what support will be provided.
- **Pricing Strategy**
Strategies in pricing can be determined by looking at the market price of a product or service in question or similar.
- **Distribution Strategy**
Describe how the distribution strategy will be used for the product to reach the customer.
- **Marketing Communication Strategy**
Communication strategy using advertising and promotions, to attract customers.
- **Sales Strategy**
Strategies in selling products or services. Analysis of salespeople and customer support should be performed.
- **Sales and Marketing Forecasts**
Estimated marketing can be done with 2 methods, namely:
 - **Comparable Method**
The method is based on what the company has accomplished.
 - **Build-up Method**
Identify all sources of revenue from a business process

3.7. Operational plan

There are 3 main components, namely:

- **Operation Strategy:** The overall strategy includes financial, time, flexibility and quality.
- **Scope of Operations**
The process is undertaken to determine the product or service to be generated.
- **Ongoing Operations**
Describe the planned production activities.

3.8. Development plan

There are 2 main components, namely:

- **Development Strategy:** Strategies that are carried out for product development, things that must be done so that development can run smoothly and successfully.
- **Development Timeline:** Scheduling done from the beginning of the project starts to end, and can be used to monitor progress.

3.9. Team

Describe who is involved in the company. Usually explains the role of teams, advisors, and owners of the company. Divided into 3 roles, namely:

- **Team Bios and Roles**
Determination of team members to move business processes in accordance with experience in the field of business.
- **Advisory Boards, Board of Directors, Strategic Partners, External Members**
It remains necessary for the board of directors in the newly established business to oversee business processes, as well as representatives of investors.
- **Compensation and Ownership**
Determine compensation and ownership fairly based on team members with their respective roles.

3.10. Critical risks

Estimates of the risks that will arise, therefore the company must be ready to deal with these risks. Divided into 5, namely:

- **Market Interest and Growth Potential**

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The risk of lack of selling power from products that have been produced or developed, this happens because of lack of market research, what is needed or desired by the customer.

- **Competitor Actions and Retaliation**
The belief in the goods or services offered to the market is something new and different in the industry.
- **Time and Cost of Development**
Time and cost can be an inhibiting factor when product development is ineffective.
- **Operating Expenses**
Uncontrolled operating expenses can increase continuously beyond the expectation of more oversight and management to address them.
- **Availability and Timing of Financing**
The initial difficulty experienced by newly established companies is to meet the financial needs.

3.11. Offering

Describe and estimate the amount of capital needed and how the capital will be used.

3.12. Financial plan

Determine the financial planning needed to build a business. Such as cost, revenue, cash flow, and funding.

3.13. Appendices

Analyze complementary data and clarify the business plan.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

The purpose of this business idea is through the solution of this service, this research wants to answer the needs of the community by maximizing business potential with the empowerment of information technology.

In preparing the business plan, this research uses the methodology as below.

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4.1. Gathering Information

The collection of data and information is very important, to search for sources of data and information related to the business idea, relating to market needs for products or services to be generated and as a reference for the development of future business plans.

The type of data used by the author is primary data and secondary data.

- **Primary data**

According to Sugiyono (2012), the primary data source is a source of data that directly provide data to data collectors.

The primary data collection that the author did through the way of distributing questionnaires and conduct interviews directly with the parties related to customer segmentation, the first is personal, which is the individual who is located in the developing region due to the rapid growth of property in the area and which Second is a property company.

- **Secondary Data**

According to Sugiyono (2012) secondary data source is a source of data obtained by reading, learning, and understanding through other media sourced from literature, books, and the internet.

The authors collected information from BPS (National Bureau of Statistics) and LPJK (National Development Service) data, ie data on business entities in the field of building construction, internet search results on articles and journals.

4.2. Porter's Forces

Discuss analysis to find out the business position among existing competitors, threats from newcomers, threats from replacement products, suppliers, and customers.

- The threat of new entrants

The steadily increasing use of smartphones, as well as the increasing number of smartphone repair service centre providers

- Bargaining power of buyers

The power of buyers bargaining power is quite high, as smartphone usage is increasing year by year.

- Bargaining power of suppliers

Spare part suppliers, like this business, relies heavily on the availability of equipment and replacement parts to run its business processes.

- The threat of substitute products or service

Many parties use non-original and low-quality parts, allowing the cost of total damage to be minimal. This causes many consumers who are interested to use the repair service centre with low quality because the cost is cheap even if the quality of parts replaced low.

- Rivalry among existing competitors

Other competitors have their respective advantages including experience, familiar names, large capital support, and extensive media exposure. Nevertheless, among the competitors, there are some shortcomings that the author made an advantage.

4.3. Business Model Canvas

The business model that will be done, using the framework by Osterwalder is Business Model Canvas which consists of 9 components: customer segments, value proposition, channels, customer relationship, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnership, cost structure.

4.4. Business Design

The next stage is to create a business plan that consists of:

- **Product planning**

Describe the product to be offered, including the stages in product development planning. The product to

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be generated is a web portal that can be accessed with an internet connection.

- **Marketing Plan**

Describe the way or marketing strategy is done. Using 7 strategies in marketing are target market strategy, product/service strategy, pricing strategy, distribution strategy, marketing communication strategy, sales strategy, sales and marketing forecasts.

- **Financial Plan**

Describe sources of funding and revenue prediction from business processes. Includes expenses, cash flow, and financial analysis for estimated return on investment (ROI).

- **HR planning.**

Describe the allocation of human resources and organizational structure to be established. Team building consists of several top management and works unit divisions.

4.5. Create The Website

This stage aims to create a corporate website creation plan based on a prototype that has been designed.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Executive summary

The development of technology is now growing very rapidly. Not only happen in big cities but also in small cities also have seen the entry of technological development. Coupled with changes in the lifestyle of Indonesian society, the development of technology that occurred brought a positive impact. The positive impact of these technological developments is supported by several factors that already exist.

Web-based Smartphone Repair Service is a business that offers repair service by utilizing the Internet to reach more potential customers. Indonesia is the largest contributor to smartphone sales in Southeast Asia, followed by Thailand and Malaysia.

This of course also trigger the possibility of smartphone damage that occurs due to the use of continuously.

In the service industry smartphone repair services including quite large and found in many places, such as the mall. But website-based smartphone repair services are still relatively new and not many, but the future of this industry is believed to be growing bigger.

5.2. Strategic Planning

- **Porter's 5 forces analysis**

The use of Porter's 5 forces analysis (Porter 2008) aims to determine the state of the competitive environment that affects the business processes of the company, namely:

1. The threat of new entrants

Smartphone growth continues to increase, many personal courageous to try to build their own business and play in repair services. For example for personal who opened repair service smartphone centre in various places, even the distance between one place with another very close. But the drawback is the repair is limited to android smartphone only, the repair service center for iPhone and iPad products are still somewhat small, even in the Mall though. Some repair service center that provides iPhone and iPad service even though there are some shortcomings, among others, the use of spare parts that are not original from apple centre, and service related services workmanship that exceeds the estimated time or price that can change at any time.

2. Bargaining power of buyers

The buyers in question here are the ones who are looking for iPhone and iPad repair centre. The power of buyers bargaining power is quite high, as smartphone usage is increasing year by year.

3. Bargaining power of suppliers

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The supplier in this business is the smartphone technicians themselves and spare part suppliers, as the business relies heavily on the availability of reliable technicians, equipment and replacement parts to run their business processes.

4. The threat of substitute products or service

Increased smartphone development also led to many manufacturers who specifically make spare parts as a replacement component if the smartphone is damaged. Many repair service providers use non-genuine and low-quality parts, so the total cost of damage can be minimized. This causes many consumers who are interested in using this repair service. The cheap price of counterfeit goods encourages some people to choose to buy counterfeit goods rather than the real ones. Research (MIAP) and the University of Indonesia in 2005 of 257 consumers in Jakarta and Surabaya found only 27.6 percent of consumers willing to use the original product when the price difference of counterfeit goods reached 80 percent. But if the price is only 20 percent adrift, as much as 92.6 percent prefer the original. This is certainly a considerable threat.

5. Rivalry among existing competitors

Similar smartphone repair centre which using the website as promotion media already exist, although not too many.

• **Business Model Canvas**

From 9 business model used in the business process of repair smartphone:

1. **Customer Segments**

In this business planning segmentation of consumers who want to be targeted:

Personal, which is meant individual consumers or agencies who need assistance for purposes related to smartphone repair services. The targeted area is the city of Jakarta, due to the limited range of delivery for service. Moreover, the iPhone and iPad tend to be used in middle and upper society in urban areas.

2. **Value Proposition**

Website, because it sells a web-based service. Where consumers can see the price of parts for all types in real-time.

3. **Channels**

In planning this business to be able to reach or reach its consumers is:

- Awareness, namely how consumers can recognize the services offered by way of web creation, advertising in social media, spreading brochures.
- Direct, by establishing a service centre place, so that consumers not only can use a courier to pick up his smartphone but also can come to the repair centre.

4. **Customer Relationship**

In business planning this way used to remain able to communicate with its consumers is:

- Personal assistance, which provides customer support services, as well as consulting support.
- Long-term, guarantee warranty in accordance with the repaired damage or spare parts used.

5. **Revenue Streams**

- Service sale is financing in accordance with repair services, spare parts used and smartphone sales.
- Sharing profit, payments earned from business results by sharing profits with other repair service centre who cannot fix ios smartphone and use our skill.

6. **Key Resources**

- Physical Assets, a workshop for repair and equipment needed to do the work can be tools such as blower, multimeter, soldering, and power supply.
- Human, a smartphone service technician specializing in iPhone and iPad.
- Intellectual: website, branding / corporate brand, consumer data.
- Financial, corporate financial resources in the form of cash, credit, funding, etc.

7. **Key Activities**

- Problem solving, the intention is to promote service that can solve problems related to price and quality assurance, and also the delivery of smartphone shuttle service so as to provide convenience for

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consumers who have not had time to visit the service shop.

- Web development is to provide information related to the price of spare parts real-time, so customers can find out how much expenditure will be incurred based on the damage which analysed by the technician.

8. **Key Partnership**

- Competition, the intention is to establish cooperation with other service providers, who have limited service in the field of iPhone and iPad.
- Strategic alliance, which is cooperation with parts supplier company.

9. **Cost Structure**

- Fixed cost, is the cost of expenses to hire technicians.
- Variable cost, ie the cost incurred depends on the amount of spare parts usage.
- Marketing is the cost incurred to market / promote the service.

5.3. *Business Planning*

• **Product Description**

1. **Website**

Products or services of this business is a website that serves as a medium of information for potential customers to see the list price of spare parts or other types of services in real-time, they can make a booking via the website to use the shuttle service smartphone.

2. **SB Admin**

Advantages of Web-based Smartphone Repair Service: display data spare parts, reparation, and service list OS real-time. Therefore admin using SB Admin that can be used to update the data periodically.

• **Marketing Planning**

Marketing planning uses the STP approach (Segmentation, targeting, and positioning) and the marketing mix.

1. **Segmentation**

a. Geographical segmentation:

The coverage of Web-based Smartphone Repair Service is limited in Jakarta.

b. Demographic coverage:

Limited to personal and cooperation between business entities engaged in services but limited to the type of iPad and iPhone.

c. Behavioral Segmentation:

The business people who have busy with their activity and not have much time to bring their smartphone to be repaired.

2. **Targeting**

Based on the segmentation that has been done, determined the main target of this website is a project from an individual located in Jakarta.

3. **Positioning**

Making the website as the main goal for prospective customers who need help smartphone repair service. With the services offered are expected to assist in meeting the needs of prospective customers.

• **Marketing Mix**

1. **Product**

a. a website which offers smartphone repair service that is specialized in iPad and iPhone. Services offered are repair, replacement spare parts, and software upgrades.

b. Sales of iPad and iPhone smartphones. Due to the service centre housed in one of the mall's shop, then the iPad and iPhone sales can also increase the monthly income.

2. **Place**

Internet is used as a marketing medium, and also open a repair service centre for consumers who want to come directly to hand over the smartphone they want to fix.

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3. Promotion

Promotions will be made by creating ads on Google AdWords, social media, and also to increase the sale value of this repair service will be given software upgrade service, pickup service, and free checking service during the promotion.

4. Price

Pricing is adjusted for service repair fee. After examination of the smartphone to check the damage, then the fee is set based on spare parts or damage in the service.

5. People

The manpower required in this business plan is technician because smartphone repair service is in need of technicians who are reliable especially in the field of service of iPad and iPhone.

6. Process

The work process begins from the prospective customer's demand for service needs, the request can be done through the website or number that has been provided. Through the website, customers must fill in personal data and problems about the damage experienced by the smartphone (iPhone / iPad). After data is filled and sent, technicians will receive an email notification that there is a new request from the customers. After that, will be done the provision of information while related to the damage experienced and the possibility of costs incurred by prospective customers. If the customer agrees, the technician will come to the specified location according to the place and date requested by the customer.

Once checked, the customer will be notified of the damage after being checked directly by the technician, after which the smartphone will be repaired at the consumer location or taken to the workshop if it requires more action that requires the use of soldering and other tools.

7. Physical evidence

Improvement processes requiring replacement of parts will be brought back to the consumer as evidence, as well as during the process of costumer will be given evidence in the form of photos related to the damage that occurred on his smartphone through sending images via email or whatsapp.

- **Financial Planning**

Financial planning for Web-based Smartphone Repair Service is done to determine and ensure the profitability of this business. With an initial capital of 100,000,000 million rupiah, which comes from its own capital. Planning is structured by making a projection for 4 years for revenue and expenses. Projected financial statements, consisting of the income statement, cash flow statement, net present value (NPV), payback period (PP), and return on investment (ROI).

1. NPV

To find out whether the business website is possible to run needs to be analyzed by net present value (NPV). The assumptions made in the NPV calculations are as follows:

The reference rate or interest rate used to calculate PV is based on the deposit guarantee interest rate of commercial banks from the Deposit Insurance Corporation (LPS) for the period of January 16, 2018 - May 14, 2018, at 8.25%.

Information	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Income		Rp. 256,300,000	Rp. 269,200,000	Rp. 282,200,000	Rp. 296,050,000
Spending	Rp. -100,000,000	Rp. -189,193,008	Rp. -198,113,508	Rp. -207,474,584	Rp. -217,305,713
Net Cash Flow	Rp. -100,000,000	Rp. 67,106,992	Rp. 71,086,492	Rp. 74,725,416	Rp. 78,744,287
DF ()	1.000	0.926	0.8570	0.7940	0.7350
Present Value	Rp. -100,000,000	Rp. 62,141,075	Rp. 60,921,123	Rp. 59,331,980	Rp. 57,877,051
Nett Present Value (NPV)	Rp. -100,000,000	Rp. -37,858,925	Rp. 23,062,198	Rp. 82,394,178	Rp. 140,271,229

2. Payback Period

Payback Period = 1 year 7 months

Payback Period of this business is smaller than the investment period of 4 years, then the business is profitable and worth proceeding.

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3. Return On Investment

Return on Investment Analysis (ROI) is calculated by comparing the total profit (loss) of the company after tax for 4 years which amounted to Rp. 221,135,387 to the investment value of Rp. 100,000,000.

Information	Total
Overall Profit and Loss after tax for 4 years	Rp. 221,135,387
Investment in year 0	Rp. 100,000,000
	Rp. 121,135,387
ROI	121.13%

ROI was obtained at about 121.13% in 4 years. So it can be concluded that the investment of smartphone repair website based bring profits.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the description and analysis that has been presented in the previous chapters, it can be deduced from the formulation of previous problems:

- Website and SB Admin page have been created and completed. The results of the test show that the technical input of personal data, the selection of smartphones in the price list and inputting and editing commands performed on the page SB Admin runs well without constraints. The advantages of the website display the cost of repair service and spare parts of all types of smartphones for the type of iPhone and iPad real-time. While the lack of consumers is not provided login page to the dashboard page that serves to see the progress of the smartphone being repaired.
- By doing analysis and projection of finance for 4 years got the result that the business of smartphone repair is very feasible to run. This is supported by the results of the analysis of net present value (NPV) which is positive, the payback period is achieved only within 1 year 7 months, and also the achievement of return on investment (ROI) equal to 121.13% or 30.28% per year.

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